

There are three species of bear native to North America. Most quite a few North American bears. The commonest is the American black bear, adopted by the brown bear after which the polar bear. Discovered all through Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Weighs 200 to 600 pounds. Might be darkish or light brown (cinnamon), typically even white. Not always black in color. 900,000 and never threatened. □□ Location: The American black bear will be found all through Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Nevertheless, some subspecies such as the Louisiana black bear are protected under the U.S. □□ Dimension: Adults weigh 200 to 600 pounds and are 5 to six ft in size. □□ Features: Most black bears are black, but their fur can vary from dark brown to lighter brown (cinnamon) and even white on uncommon occasions. They have pointed ears and a straight face. Of all of the bear species black bears are a few of the best at climbing timber. Their comparatively smaller size and shorter claws make them fast and nimble to climb bushes for protection, meals, and even hibernation. The majority of their weight loss plan is vegetarian consisting of berries, plant shoots, and nuts. □□ Eating regimen: Their varied weight-reduction plan gives them the power to stay in a large range of habitats. They also eat insects, fish, and carrion. □□ Dangerous? They're the probably bear to be encountered in the backcountry. And yes, they love honey. The grizzly and Kodiak are the two subspecies of brown bears in North America. Most widespread bear species are discovered in the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Center East. Brown bears are essentially the most widespread of all bear species, found in the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Center East. Grizzlies are accountable for almost all bear attacks in North America, with forty six per year. Although their conservation standing is "least concern", their unfold-out nature and lowered habitat make many of the small remaining pockets fragile. The 200,000 brown bears of the world occupy a wide variety of habitats spanning deserts, forests, and mountains. All brown bears share a large construct, a dish-shaped face, and a shoulder hump. Their hair is lighter at the tips, which led to the title of the most famous subspecies, grizzly. Brown bears forage on roots, berries, insects, and fish, and some even hunt young mammals reminiscent of elk and moose. Their coloration varies from light blonde to darkish brown. The two subspecies in North America are the grizzly and Kodiak. □□ Location: Grizzly bears are discovered in the northern USA, Canada, and Alaska. □□ Size: Adults weigh 400 to 790 pounds, are 6.5 ft long, and have a shoulder height of 3. Three ft. □□ Weight loss program: Grizzlies eat berries, nuts, salmon and have been known to prey on large mammals. Coastal grizzlies are usually larger than these found in the Rocky Mountains attributable to a richer food regimen. Each year there are forty six assaults and 6 deaths. □□ Dangerous? Known for their aggressive behavior, grizzlies are chargeable for the most bear assaults in North America. □□ Location: Kodiak bears are only discovered on the Kodiak Islands, an archipelago in southwestern Alaska. □□ Measurement: Kodiak bears are almost as massive as polar bears, weighing 600 to 1,400 pounds, 8 toes lengthy, and 4 feet tall on the shoulder. □□ Weight-reduction plan: Their food regimen is just like mainland grizzly bears. However, on account of extra plentiful food sources, the islands can assist a denser bear inhabitants. Geographic isolation from the mainland allowed the 3,500 Kodiak bears to develop into their very own subspecies. This has led to a extra complicated social construction which leads to less battle between bears. □□ Dangerous? Like grizzlies, Kodiak bears may be aggressive. Attributable to their isolation, there is only one attack on humans every other yr. Largest species of bear in the world weighing between 800 and 1,300 pounds. Weight loss plan is mostly made up of meat, typically from seals. □□ Location: Polar bears are the biggest bears and largest land carnivores on the planet. Fur appears white but is actually clear. The world's 20,000 to 30,000 polar bears vary in the snow-coated arctic ice in Alaska, Canada, Russia, and Norway. □□ Size: Adult polar bears are 800 to 1,300 pounds and may be 7 to 10 ft tall. They're a threatened species because of lack of habitat from local weather change. Despite their huge size polar bears could be quick, sustaining a 6 mph tempo within the water. □□ Options: In comparison with different bears, polar bears have a slimmer body, slender head, longer neck, and paddle-like paws. For context, swimmer Michael Phelps received Olympic gold medals with a 4.7 mph pace! □□ Food regimen: Their food regimen consists mostly of animals, especially seals which they'll scent from a mile away. Though they seem white, their fur is definitely clear and their pores and skin is black. □□ Harmful? Polar bears might be extraordinarily dangerous. They see people as potential prey. Attacks are rare as a result of remote nature of their habitat. Recognized for its cream coloration chest blazes. At 300 pounds one of the smaller bears. Easy to tame and infrequently frequent in circuses. □□ Location: The Asian black bear is present in forests and shrublands across Asia from Iran to Japan. The population is estimated at 40,000 to 50,000 and is considered weak. □□ Measurement: One of many smaller species, adults weigh around 300 pounds and stand 47 to seventy five inches tall. □□ Weight-reduction plan: Relying on the season it commonly feeds on small mammals, birds, fish, mollusks and carcasses or grasses, fruits, berries, seeds, insects, and honey. Assaults on humans are increasing as

individuals encroach on their habitat. □□ Dangerous? They are one of the easiest bears to tame (and subsequently widespread in circuses), however Asian black bears are extra aggressive than their North American counterparts. Found solely in China. 99% of its food plan is bamboo. The truth is, the second individual in historical past to receive a facial transplant was mauled by an Asian black bear whereas defending his sheep. Known for its iconic white face, eye patches, and striped physique. □□ Location: Pandas are discovered only in China. Solely 1,500 to 2,000 remain within the wild and they are thought of a vulnerable species. □□ Size: Pandas weigh round 300 pounds and could be over four feet tall, a powerful feat contemplating they weigh solely about 3.5 ounces at start. It also has a detailed cousin, the Qinling panda which has the same pattern in gentle brown and white. □□ Food regimen: In contrast to other bears the panda's weight loss plan is homogeneous; 99% of what they eat is bamboo. □□ Features: The enormous panda is iconic for its white face, black eye patches, and striped body. All that fibrous bamboo retains them common: they poop over 40 instances a day! □□ Dangerous? Attacks are rare but dangerous, given that pandas have one in all the highest chunk forces of any carnivore. Smallest Bear weighing fifty five to 143 pounds. Found in South East Asia. 8 to 10-inch lengthy tongue for slurping up insects and honey. □□ Location: The Sun bear is found in the forest and shrubland of South East Asia and India. It's the least studied bear and. Its population is unsure but thought-about vulnerable and on the decline as a consequence of lack of habitat and poaching. Sun bears are hunted for his or her gallbladders and other physique parts utilized in traditional medicines. □□ Measurement: They stand solely 39 to 55 inches and weigh fifty five to 143 pounds making them the smallest bear. □□ Features: Sun bears have strongly curved claws, small rounded ears, and a brief snout. They are named for their pale, horseshoe-formed chest patch that appears like a rising solar. In addition they eat seeds, fruit, birds, and deer. □□ Food regimen: Sun bears tear apart bushes and nests to eat ants, bees, beetles, termites, and honey. Their love of honey has given them the nickname "honey bears." In actual fact, they have an incredibly lengthy tongue (8-10 inches) for slurping up insects and honey. Native to South Asia. □□ Dangerous? Due to its shy nature, attacks are uncommon. Long, shaggy fur and mane gave them the name sloth bear. Sloth bears are feared by rhinos and elephants. □□ Location: The Sloth bear is found within the low elevation savanna and shrubland of India, Nepal, and Sri Lanka. With a declining inhabitants of lower than 20,000, they're considered vulnerable. □□ Dimension: They are 55 to 75 inches long and weigh 200 to 300 pounds. □□ Options: With their lengthy shaggy fur and mane, they're easy to inform aside from other Asiatic bears. In reality, they are very quick and might out-gallop people. European explorers mistook them for sloths after seeing them hanging the wrong way up from timber. They're noisy, messy eaters tearing up termite mounds with their massive curved claws. □□ Eating regimen: Their weight-reduction plan consists of termites, ants, and fruit. □□ Harmful? They're one of the crucial aggressive bears, with the most assaults on people, largely as a consequence of surprise encounters. They blow the mud round with huge puffs and suck the ants up so loudly they can be heard 600 feet away. Sloth bears stand their ground if threatened and do not mix effectively with rhinos and elephants, usually charging at each other when in proximity. Solely South American bear. World's final brief-faced bear. The identify "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings round their eyes that seem like glasses. This weak species of 13,000 to 18,000 remaining bears are discovered in the cloud forests of the Andes from Argentina to Ecuador. □□ Dimension: They are mid-sized, weighing 175 to 275 pounds, and standing 47 to 79 inches tall. □□ Location: The spectacled bear is the world's last quick-confronted bear and the one bear native to South America. □□ Features: The title "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings [pooch bear soft toy](#) around their eyes that sometimes appear like glasses. They spend most of their time in trees the place they build nest platforms, sleep and jealously guard precious fruit and carcasses. □□ Weight loss program: Spectacled bears are principally herbivores with a weight loss program consisting of largely cactus, bromeliad, palm hearts, and fruit, but they'll opportunistically eat mammals like rabbits and tapirs. □□ Dangerous? Dwelling in remote mountains, these shy bears would be the least dangerous of all bear species. Their our bodies are smaller than polar bears however larger than grizzlies. The Grolar bear (aka Pizzly) is a uncommon hybrid of a polar bear and a grizzly bear that occurs in each nature and captivity. Grolar bear conduct is closer to the polar bear. They feature the long necks of polar bears and the shoulder humps of grizzlies. In captivity, they've been documented stomping toys, just like how polar bears break ice. Black-brown hybrid bears have been bred in captivity, notably at the London Zoo in 1859, however have not been confirmed within the wild. In 1986, a suspected grizzly-brown hybrid was shot however DNA tests had been unable to find out what kind of bear it was. Adorable koalas aren't bears, they're burly marsupials. Water bears aren't bears either, they are indestructible, microscopic animals that can survive in house. Most bear attacks occur when a bear is startled or protecting their cubs. Pink pandas? They're in their own household which can be nearer cousins with skunks and raccoons than bears. 1. BEWARE OF YOUR

SURROUNDINGS. Look ahead to bear scat and bear tracks which will point out a bear is nearby, by which case you need to be extra vigilant. Here are just a few suggestions you need to use to forestall bear encounters and keep you and your hiking buddies protected. 2. **MAKE NOISE.** This helps bears know you are here so they don't accidentally startle them. Consider attaching a bear bell to your pack. 3. **KEEP YOUR DISTANCE.** Whereas you might have nice intentions, a bear is likely to really feel threatened when it sees you approaching and defend itself. 3. **Safe YOUR SCENTED Objects (AT CAMP).** If you see a bear, do not try to approach or feed it. This contains meals, but in addition your toiletries, for example. Whichever methodology you select, ensure it is not less than 200 feet away from your tent so you do not appeal to bears to your campsite. 4. **Stay CALM.** When you meet a bear, do not run. Attempt to make your self look as big as attainable, waving your arms above your head. It's also possible to prolong a jacket above your head to make your self look larger. Lock these things in a bear canister or use a bear bag to hang them up in a tree. Don't scream or attempt to scare the bear. 5. **USE BEAR SPRAY (AS A final RESORT).** Converse to it calmly and slowly again away. Full instruction on how to use bear spray right here. If the bear is dangerously shut (30 feet) or is charging at you, pull out your bear spray and use it in 1-2 second bursts, aiming slightly downward. 6. **Fight Again.** If all else fails and a bear attacks you, don't play lifeless. Which bear is the biggest? Averaging 900-1500 lbs, 8.0 to 8.4 ft lengthy, and 4.0 to 5.25 toes tall, the largest bear by each size and weight is the polar bear. The biggest ever recorded was 2,200 lbs. Fight again with all of your strength and hope that it's going to back down. Which bear is probably the most dangerous? All bears are dangerous if provoked. Globally, the Asian black bear is understood for the most assaults. When in bear country, it's always clever to hold bear spray. It's effectively deserved, particularly when cubs are around. Every year there are roughly 46 grizzly attacks, 6 resulting in demise. In North America, grizzly bears have essentially the most fearsome status. Which bear is the strongest? Whereas you're most prone to see an American black bear, on common there is just one attack per yr. By way of uncooked chunk energy, measured in Newtons, the polar bear's chunk reigns supreme. All bears are robust and to not be messed with. When utilizing the chunk drive quotient (chew energy relative to dimension), the solar bear packs essentially the most punch. Originally named "Hotfoot Teddy", Smokey Bear was a black bear cub found in the spring of 1950 after a wildfire in New Mexico. He had climbed a tree to escape the fireplace but sustained burns on his paws and hind legs. Quickly after he turned an icon and to this present day is the star of the longest-working public service announcement marketing campaign. Yogi Bear is an animated bear identified for his love of "pic-a-nic" baskets. More importantly Yogi Bear has inspired countless through-hikers to try and grasp the art of "yogi-ing", the act of not fairly begging but receiving favors from strangers. Baloo is a sloth bear, although he has some traits of the Asian black bear. He is an easygoing, friendly bear who lives a accountability-free way of life. He additionally might be the primary bear to receive his pilot's license. Earlier than he was the storybook teddy bear, Winnie the Pooh was a black bear from Canada which the author's son usually would visit on the London Zoo. Winnie is brief for "Winnipeg," the town in Canada near the place he was from. Chris additionally wrote The way to Hike the Appalachian Trail. Equal components backpacking food and ultralight gear. After thru-hiking the Appalachian Trail, Chris Cage created Greenbelly to offer quick, filling and balanced meals to backpackers. Get epic tips, guides and the way-to's in your inbox every two weeks.

